

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF COMPLICATIONS OF TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10642966>

Abstract : diabetes mellitus, known to the world as one of the oldest diseases, does not lose its relevance in the modern world. One of the main problems of diabetes mellitus remains its complications. This article is devoted to the pathophysiology of type 1 diabetes mellitus

Keywords. Diabetes mellitus, complications, pathophysiology

Chronic complications of diabetes mellitus can be divided into *microvascular* , which are unique to the state of carbohydrate metabolism disorders, and *macrovascular* , which can also occur in people without diabetes. Microvascular complications include diabetic retinopathy , nephropathy and neuropathy . Microvascular complications develop with the same frequency in both type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus, resulting from the interaction of a number of metabolic, genetic and other factors, among which the hyperglycemia factor is of greatest importance. Epidemiological and prospective studies indicate a direct relationship between glycemic levels and the degree of progression of microvascular complications. Evidence that the hyperglycemia factor underlies various manifestations of microvascular complications is data on combined damage to the fundus, kidneys, and peripheral nervous system. Thus, the risk of developing the proliferative stage of diabetic retinopathy is 5–10 times higher in patients with the proteinuric stage of nephropathy.

What is the influence of factors such as age, gender, duration of the disease? Patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus, whose onset of the disease occurs before puberty , have a higher risk of developing diabetic nephropathy and associated early mortality [1]. In patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, taking into account older age (when diabetes usually develops), there are a number of additional factors that determine the rate of progression of microvascular complications of diabetes. For example, hypertension and dyslipidemia can often precede carbohydrate intolerance, significantly increasing the risk of early microcirculatory changes. The influence of gender on the incidence and extent of microvascular disorders has been the subject of interest in many studies, but it should be noted that the association only exists for a higher risk of developing diabetic polyneuropathy in men. *Along with the degree of compensation, the duration of diabetes mellitus is the most important factor influencing the incidence of microangiopathy* . It would be a mistake to simplify this association to a

postulate: the longer the duration, the greater the likelihood of developing complications. Thus, in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, clinically significant manifestations of microvascular complications are detected in 20–24% of cases already at the onset. At the same time, there is an obvious dependence of the development of vascular complications on the duration of the disease. Thus, in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with a disease duration of more than 15–20 years, changes in the fundus of the eye are recorded in 95% of cases.

Pathophysiology of microvascular complications in diabetes mellitus

Changes in the system of small vessels, united by the term microangiopathy, are functional and structural in nature. A characteristic feature of structural changes is *thickening of the basement membrane of the capillaries*. The most significant functional disorders are increased permeability of the vascular wall, hemodynamic disorders, changes in blood viscosity, and impaired platelet function. The thickness of the basement membrane correlates with the pressure within the capillary system. In patients with diabetes mellitus, there is an accumulation of collagen type IV, a decrease in protein glycan sulfate, chondroitin and dermatan sulfate, as well as glycoproteins such as laminin, fibronectin and enactin [2]. Hyperglycemia leads to an increase in intracellular reserves of protein kinase C through the synthesis of de novo diacylglycerol from glucose [3]. Protein kinase C plays an important role in ensuring cell function in a number of key areas, including transmitting signals from hormones, growth factors, neurotransmitters, and drugs to intracellular structures. In smooth muscle cells of the vascular wall, protein kinase C modulates DNA synthesis and hormone receptor activity.

Increased capillary permeability and hemodynamic disturbances precede *structural changes in the capillary wall*. The most indicative is an increase in intraglomerular pressure and urinary albumin excretion in response to hyperglycemia with poor metabolic control of the disease. Careful glycemic control over 12 months can normalize glomerular filtration [4]. An increase in blood flow is also observed in the retina. Confirmation that hemodynamic disturbances leading to increased intracapillary pressure can contribute to the development and progression of diabetic retinopathy is the fact that diabetic retinopathy in people with elevated systolic pressure occurs 2 or more times more often than in normotensive people [5]. Moreover, a number of observations have shown that a decrease in retinal blood flow, which occurs in

individuals with increased intraocular pressure, slows down the development of diabetic retinopathy on the side of intraorbital hypertension [6].

Increased capillary permeability

The role of increased glomerular permeability in the pathogenesis of diabetic nephropathy is beyond doubt. In both type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus, subclinical microalbuminuria is a predictor of subsequent proteinuria and the development of renal failure. The source of excess excretion of albumin and IgG is the renal glomeruli, while the excretion of β_2 -microglobulin, an indicator of the function of the renal tubular apparatus, remains normal. An increase in albumin excretion in urine is not only an indicator of a high risk of developing nephropathy, retinopathy, neuropathy, but also mortality from cardiovascular accidents. Thus, increased urinary albumin excretion is a reflection of vascular dysfunction in a broad sense, including both glomerular and retinal capillaries and the intima of large vessels.

Rheological disturbances

Important components of microangiopathy in diabetes mellitus are impaired blood viscosity and platelet dysfunction. The dysfunction of platelets is based on an imbalance between the prostaglandin system and prostacyclin, as well as a violation of the synthesis of tissue plasminogen activator. In patients with manifestations of microangiopathy, an increase in Willenbrandt factor, a glycoprotein synthesized by endothelial cells, which determines the degree of platelet adhesiveness to endothelial cells, was also detected [7].

Conclusions. Improving knowledge and skills in the pathophysiology of diabetes mellitus and the discovery of a new type of drugs for the correction of complications may lead to an improvement in the quality of life and control of complications of diabetes mellitus.

Literature:

1. Zokirov, M. (2023, June). Features of cognitive impairment in patients with HIV encephalopathy. In Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education (Vol. 1, No. 9, pp. 34-36).
2. Zokirov M.M., & Madjidova Y.N., . (2020). Correction Of Cognitive Disorder In Patients With HIV - Associated Encephalopathy. The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research, 2(07), 117-122. <https://doi.org/10.37547/TAJMSPR/Volume02Issue07-15>
3. Zokiriv, M. (2021). Correction of cognitive impairments in patients with HIV-associated encephalopathy. J. Theor. Appl. Sci, 7, 62-66.
4. Zokirov Muzaffar, & Muhammadjonov Oqilbek. (2023). Late clinical and neuroimaging manifestations of post-traumatic epilepsy and optimization of its

- treatment. Novateur Publications, 7, 1–108. Retrieved from <http://novateurpublication.org/index.php/np/article/view/114>
5. Muzaffar, Z. (2023). Anxiety and Depression in Patients with HIV Encephalopathy. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 21, 95-98.
 6. Oqilbek, M., & Muzaffar, Z. (2023). Parameters of Apoptosis and Prevention of Neuro-Like Conditions in Patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 21, 99-102.
 7. Muzaffar, Z., (2022). Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease in Combination with Cardiovascular Diseases. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 6, 150-155.

